

1 **Activation of the hyccin PI4KA lipid kinase complex subunit 1, HYCC1 in Crohn's Disease.**

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7 We used RNA-sequencing to detect alterations in energetics signaling in the whole blood in humans with IBD. We describe here activation of the hyccin PI4KA lipid complex kinase subunit 1, *HYCC1* in the hematopoietic compartment in humans with IBD.

8 Citations

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